

ETIOPATHOGENETIC RELATIONSHIP OF METABOLISM DISTURBANCE IN LAMBS WITH DYSPEPSIS IN LAMBS

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Summary

V dannoy state priveden analiz nauchnyx issledovaniy, naravlennyx na opredelenii etiopathogeneticheskoy role narusheniy metabolism u yagynyx ovtsematok s dyspepsiey yagnyat.

Keywords

Dyspepsia, Narusheniya metabolism, Suyagnye ovtsematki, Yagnyata, Neolnotsennoe kormlenie, Ketonuria, Alimentarnaya osteodisofia, Alimentarnaya dystrophy, Hypotrophy ploda, Gruppovaya profilaticheskaya tratya suyagynyx ovtsmatok.

Relevance of the topic. Decree No. PQ-4576 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 29, 2020 "On additional measures of state support for the livestock sector" and Decree No. PQ-4576 dated February 8, 2022 "On measures for further development of livestock breeding and strengthening of the feed base" In decisions No. 121, along with the urgent tasks of further increasing the number of livestock, improving their productivity and breed indicators, developing the poultry, horse breeding, rabbit breeding, fishing and beekeeping sectors, the tasks of further improving the system of combating animal diseases in the new Uzbekistan are also defined. Diseases occurring in sheep farming, which occupies one of the leading positions in the animal husbandry of our Republic, especially lamb dyspepsia, are one of the biggest obstacles in the fulfillment of these urgent tasks (B. Bakirov, N.B. Ro'ziqulov, 2018, N. Ro'ziqulov, 2022). Therefore, the development of measures to combat dyspepsia in lambs, in particular, research aimed at determining the causes of the disease, is one of the urgent challenges.

Object and methods of research. Scientific research works during 2021-2023 "Olga" LLC specializing in cattle breeding in Nurabad district of Samarkand region, sheep farm belonging to Bobir Murodalievich JK in Qamashi district of Kashkadarya region and KORAKOL and HISOR under FX conditions "Kora Kamar" in Boysun district of Surkhandarya region. it was carried out in purebred lambs and lambs. The incidence of dyspepsia in lambs born from lambs with

ketonuria, alimentary osteodystrophy, alimentary dystrophy and liver dystrophy was analyzed.

Analysis of research results. The results of the experiment are given in Table

Incidence of dyspepsia in lambs born from ewes with ketonuria, alimentary osteodystrophy, alimentary dystrophy, and hepatic dystrophy.

Table 1.

T/r	Economy	Corsets	Healthy ks	Ketone-	Alimony osteodist	Alimony.	Hepato-
1	Samar- vil. («Olga» IJ)	Number of p	5	5	5	5	5
		The obtained p	5	5	5	5	5
		Illness with dyspepsia,%	1(20/8,3%	2(40/17%)	3(60/25%)	3(60/25%)	4(80/33%)
2	Qashqa- vil. (Bobir od. XK)	Number of p	5	5	5	5	5
		The obtained p	5	5	5	5	5
		Dyspepsia. sick with.,%	1(20/10%)	2(40/20%)	2(40/20%)	2(40/20%)	3(60/30%)
3	Surxon- vil. («Qora ar» FX)	Number of p	5	5	5	5	5
		The obtained p	5	5	5	5	5
		Dyspepsia. sick with.,%	- (0/0%)	1(20/14%)	2(40/28%)	2(40/28%)	2(40/28%)
4	TOTAL	Number of p	15	15	15	15	15
		The obtained p	15	15	15	15	15
		Dyspepsia. sick with.,%	2(13/6,6%)	5(33/17%)	7(47/23%)	7(47/23%)	9(60/30%)

The results of the conducted research showed that the average incidence rate of dyspepsia was 20% in lambs born from healthy lambs under the conditions of "Olga" LLC specialized in cattle breeding in Nurabad district of Samarkand region, 40% in lambs born from lambs infected with ketonuria, and 40% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary osteodystrophy. it was 60% in lambs, 60% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary dystrophy, and 80% in lambs born with liver

dystrophy. It was found that the share of ketonuria in causing dyspepsia in this region is on average 17%, that of alimentary osteodystrophy is 25%, that of alimentary dystrophy is 25%, that of liver dystrophy is 33%, and lambs born from healthy lambs are 8.3%.

The incidence of dyspepsia in lambs born from healthy ewes in the conditions of Bobir Murodalyevich JK sheep farm in Qamashi district of Kashkadarya region is on average 20%, 40% in lambs born from ewes with ketonuria, 40% in lambs born from ewes with alimentary osteodystrophy, it was 40% in lambs born from ewes with alimentary dystrophy, 60% in lambs born with liver dystrophy. In this case, it was found that the share of ketonuria in causing dyspepsia in this region is on average 20%, that of alimentary osteodystrophy is 20%, that of alimentary dystrophy is 20%, that of liver dystrophy is 30%, and lambs born from healthy lambs is 10%.

Dyspepsia was not observed in lambs born from healthy lambs under the conditions of "Black belt" FX in Boysun district of Surkhandarya region. The average rate of dyspepsia in lambs born from lambs with ketonuria was 20%, 40% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary osteodystrophy, 40% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary dystrophy, 40% in lambs born with liver dystrophy. In this case, it was found that the share of ketonuria in causing dyspepsia in this region is on average 14%, that of limentary osteodystrophy is 28%, that of alimentary dystrophy is 28%, that of liver dystrophy is 28%.

In general, the rate of dyspepsia in Karakol lambs in the regions of Samarkand, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan where Karakol sheep are raised is on average 13% in lambs born from conditionally healthy lambs, 33% in lambs born from lambs infected with ketonuria, 47% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary osteodystrophy. %, 47% in lambs born from lambs with alimentary dystrophy, 60% in lambs born from lambs with liver dystrophy. In this case, it was found that among metabolic disorders causing dyspepsia in this area, the share of ketonuria is on average 17%, that of alimentary osteodystrophy is 23%, that of alimentary dystrophy is 23%, that of liver dystrophy is 30%, and in lambs born from healthy lambs it is 6.6%.

conclusion:

1. Dyspepsia of Karakol lambs in the regions of Samarkand, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan where Karakol sheep are raised was caused by metabolic disturbances in the body of the ewes. in cold lambs, this indicator reaches 33%, 47% during alimentary osteodystrophy, 47% during alimentary dystrophy, and 60% during liver dystrophy.

2. In this case, 30% of dyspepsia in lambs due to antenatal metabolic causes was caused by lambs born from lambs with liver dystrophy, 23% by lambs born with alimentary osseodystrophy, another 23% by lambs born with alimentary dystrophy, and the remaining 17% consists of lambs born from lambs infected with ketonuria.

3. Although lambs with dyspepsia are born from healthy lambs, their share among all antenatal causes is on average 6.6%.

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